

Artificial Intelligence For Small And Medium-Scale Enterprises (SMES) In Nigeria: Highlighting Key Applications (APPs), Benefits And Challenges

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ABSTRACT

This study highlights artificial intelligence for small- and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) by identifying key applications, benefits, and challenges through interviews and content analysis. This study underscores the substantial AI applications for small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs), such as chatbots and virtual assistants, robotic process automation, recommendation systems, learning machines, and computer vision. Furthermore, the research examines the potential advantages, including enhanced customer service, reduced staff expenses, increased efficiency and productivity, tailored offers and services, and optimized business processes. The research examines several obstacles that small- and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria face when implementing artificial intelligence (AI). These difficulties include the shortage of specialized personnel and knowledge, data privacy and security concerns, the high cost of integrating and maintaining AI systems, worries about job displacement, limited financial resources, inadequate infrastructure, and low digital maturity. To address these issues, the study recommends that the government develop a national strategy for AI that encourages, integrates, and maintains its use among SMEs in Nigeria. It is also suggested that the government and SMEs management should work together to create secure data mechanisms and provide staff training and skill development to enhance AI capabilities. Lastly, the management of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) should work towards creating a smooth integration of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies into their current business operations to achieve optimal growth and development.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Small and Medium Enterprises, AI applications, Benefits and Challenges

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the rapid development of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has greatly impacted the field of artificial intelligence (AI). AI has significantly influenced many aspects of modern society, including the operation of small- and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs). As AI technologies continue to progress rapidly, an increasing number of SMEs are incorporating AI into their business strategies to gain a competitive advantage (Gonesh et al., 2023). The successful application of AI tools in industrial settings is crucial for the efficient processing and interpretation of data, which can benefit both

companies and their customers. The success of SMEs is especially critical, as they are the backbone of the development of every economy in the world (Szedlak et al., 2020).

Artificial intelligence (AI) is widely regarded as a vital future technology for solving intricate business challenges. As per Jadhav (2021), AI has emerged as the preferred solution for tackling complex business problems across various industrial sectors, particularly among small and medium enterprises (SMEs). In fact, certain countries, such as Germany and Malaysia, view the integration of AI into SMEs as a key factor for future national growth. For instance, the Malaysian government has emphasized the development of AI skills among SMEs as a strategic tool for driving future economic development. It is worth noting that SMEs account for an impressive 98.5% of all businesses in Malaysia and contribute a substantial 36.6% to the nation's GDP (Corp and Wei, 2018). In alignment with this perspective, the German Government has formulated a national strategy for AI, with the aim of maintaining and enhancing the competitive position of the German economy through the extensive use of AI-based technologies and tools (Bundesregierung, 2018). Artificial intelligence can be seamlessly integrated into various aspects of business operations to boost the growth and development of SMEs in Nigeria. Ebuka et al. (2023) have highlighted a range of business areas where AI can be implemented in SMEs to gain competitive advantages, including customer service, production, procurement, marketing, research and development, and human resources, among others.

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) play a vital role in the growth and development of many countries, as they serve as primary catalysts for economic expansion within communities by generating employment opportunities and providing local citizens with avenues for economic advancement (Bandari, 2019). Moreover, these enterprises act as agents of innovation and creativity in many economies, as they are more responsive to environmental discontinuities. By incorporating artificial intelligence (AI) into their operations, SMEs can enhance their capabilities, streamline their processes, and adapt to shifting market dynamics (Gonesh et al., 2023). Despite the wide availability of AI technologies and their impressive performance potential, SMEs often face challenges in taking full advantage of them (Brodny & Tutak, 2022). Furthermore, SMEs typically encounter significant obstacles when implementing cutting-edge technologies, such as AI, due to limited resources and expertise (Schonberger, 2023). Sanjeev et al. (2020) argue that the implementation of AI in small and medium enterprises alters the way they conduct business. However, the factors that determine the success or failure of AI system implementation in small firms in Nigeria remain unclear.

Although certain nations view the implementation of artificial intelligence (AI) in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) as a means of promoting economic growth and development in the future, Nigeria has demonstrated a relatively low adoption rate of AI in its SME sector. According to Ebuka et al. (2023), the majority of SMEs in Nigeria continue to operate manually, thereby limiting their potential for AI deployment and preventing them from achieving greater size and scale. This paper aims to address this issue by exploring the use of AI in SMEs, including its key applications, benefits, and challenges.

Concept of Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Artificial intelligence is a field of computer systems that are designed to perform tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as speech recognition, problem solving, and learning (Gonesh et al., 2023). According to Arakpogun et al. (2021), AI is a collection of Information and Communication Technologies that imitate human intelligence. Grover, Kar, and Dwivedi (2022) defined AI as the ability of a system to acquire knowledge by evaluating data obtained from its external environment, which is then utilized to adapt to existing plans or generate new ones to effectively respond to changes in the environment (Ebuka et al., 2023). Artificial intelligence is often referred to as machine intelligence, displayed by machines, as opposed to the intelligence displayed by human beings. The term AI is used to describe machines that exhibit cognitive capabilities, allowing them to communicate intelligently with each other by passing signals (Sanjeev et al., 2020). Machine learning is a process by which machines generate signals.

Concept of Small and Medium-Scale Enterprises

The European Commission (2003) defines small- and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) as businesses with fewer than 250 employees and either a turnover below 50 million euros or a balance sheet total under 43 million euros. Osondu (1991) notes that the Central Bank of Nigeria categorized SMEs as manufacturing or service entities with capital not exceeding N150,000 in manufacturing and equipment. Additionally, the Central Bank of Nigeria's 2005 Small and Medium Enterprise Investment Scheme (SMEIS) guidelines described SMEs as ventures with a maximum asset base of 200 million naira, excluding land and working capital, without specifying employee limits (Etuk, Etuk, & Baghebo, 2014). The National Council of Industries (2009) characterizes SMEs as businesses with total costs not exceeding 200 million naira, excluding land. These varying definitions emphasize that SMEs are characterized by their limited asset base and workforce size. Notwithstanding their small scale, SMEs play a significant role in economic development, as their aggregate impact often surpasses that of large-scale enterprises.

Artificial Intelligence applications (Apps) for Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs)

AI applications are of different types; some can be utilized for education and farming, and some can be utilized for business activities. AI applications can be incorporated into the growth and development of SMEs in Nigeria.

- 1) **Chatbots/Virtual Assistants:** this AI will revolutionize customer support for SMEs. This AI can handle customers' inquiries, resolve issues, and provide 24/7 support, which will lead to an increase in customer satisfaction and retention. Schönberger (2023) affirmed that with the adoption of chatbots or virtual assistants, SMEs will recognize the value of automated customer interactions and the potential to improve user experience and engagement through AI-powered conversational interfaces.
- 2) **Recommendation systems:** This AI will enable SMEs to deliver personalized customer experiences at scale. By leveraging AI algorithms, businesses can analyze customer behavior, preferences, and feedback, allowing tailored product recommendations and targeted marketing campaigns.
- 3) **Machine Learning:** The utilization of this AI tool will enable SMEs to ensure better quality control and production monitoring. This will enable SMEs to predict future trends, customer demands, and market fluctuations.
- 4) **Predictive Analytics:** Utilization of this AI tool will enable SMEs to streamline inventory management and reduce costs. It will also help SMEs ensure product availability where and when customers need it. Predictive analytics enables SMEs to perform a comprehensive analysis of vast quantities of data, thereby facilitating the identification of patterns, valuable insights, and potential avenues for business expansion (Ebuka et al., 2023).
- 5) **Robotic Process Automation (RPA):** RPA is an AI application that helps automate business processes using a well-defined rule engine. It helps automate routine and repetitive tasks, such as maintenance will be efficiently handled. This involves the consumption of structured data and rules or data-based decision trees (Aguirre & Rodriguez, 2017).
- 6) **Natural Language Processing:** This AI tool will enable SMEs to automate various tasks such as customer service, content creation, and saving time and resources. It will also help personalize marketing messages and improve customer engagement by providing relevant and timely information to customers.

Benefits of using AI tools in Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs)

AI tools have the potential to benefit small- and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria by improving business processes, customer services, and increasing efficiency and productivity. AI can also help overcome language barriers and facilitate market expansion through language translation and localization, as well as enhance e-commerce personalization to increase conversion rates and customer satisfaction. These potential benefits demonstrate the potential for AI to play a role in Nigeria's economic growth and development.

Furthermore, the incorporation of AI in financial management has the potential to increase the efficiency of small businesses in managing their financial affairs. Financial management tools powered by artificial intelligence offer significant benefits for various financial tasks, including tracking expenses, managing invoices, and predicting financial outcomes. Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) can enhance their financial management processes and boost efficiency in handling monetary matters by implementing these technologies (Ebuka et al., 2023).

Additionally, the implementation of AI in SMEs accelerates innovation by enabling rapid prototyping and product development. SMEs can utilize AI-powered tools to test and refine ideas, minimize the time to market, and reduce the risk associated with product launches. Moreover, the utilization of AI-driven marketing tools enables SMEs to develop targeted marketing campaigns with higher conversion rates. Analyzing customer behavior and preferences can help identify the most effective channels and content for reaching the target audience.

Challenges of Implementation of AI in SMEs in Nigeria

Small- and medium-sized enterprises frequently encounter various obstacles when implementing cutting-edge technological advancements, including artificial intelligence. According to Schönberger (2023), the adoption of AI in organizations presents a number of challenges that can impact the successful integration of these innovative technologies into existing business operations. The following are some of the challenges that small and medium-sized enterprises in Nigeria may face when adopting artificial intelligence into their operations.

1. Lack of expertise and experience: The primary challenge faced by small and medium-sized enterprises in Nigeria when incorporating AI into their operations is a lack of technical knowledge. Szedlak et al. (2020) argued that a dearth of expertise is the primary barrier to AI adoption in SMEs.

2. High cost of implementation and maintenance: The expense associated with implementing and maintaining AI in SMEs is significant, which means that not all businesses can afford to incorporate AI into their operations. Ebuka et al. (2023) stated that small and medium-sized enterprises and their owners in Nigeria often believe that the cost of deploying or adopting AI and its various technologies is prohibitive in terms of cost. As a result, they tend to shy away from them.

3) Data Security and Privacy: The implementation of AI in Nigerian SMEs raises concerns about data security and privacy. The absence of an effective security infrastructure hampers the proper integration of AI in Nigerian SMEs.

4) Impact on Job Security: Some SMEs in Nigeria resist the adoption of AI for emotional reasons, such as the fear of job losses. They believe that the incorporation of technology in businesses leads to the displacement of workers and the loss of their primary source of income (Ebuka et al., 2023).

5) Challenges in Integrating AI with Existing Systems: The implementation of AI tools in existing businesses poses certain challenges. According to Ebuka et al. (2023), the "this is how we used to do it" mentality has deterred businesses, particularly those with limited human or material resources in Nigeria, from adopting technology and AI in their operations. They are hesitant to change traditional methods, sometimes due to fear of the unknown consequences of embracing AI. Therefore, it is essential for SMEs to establish a seamless interface between AI technologies and their existing business structures to ensure the optimal utilization of AI for their growth and development.

CONCLUSION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies reshape how businesses operate and innovate. As AI advances, SMEs must embrace their potential and harness their power to remain competitive in the ever-evolving business landscape. By incorporating AI-driven solutions, SMEs can unlock new opportunities for growth, efficiency, and success, positioning their ventures at the forefront of the business future. Therefore, incorporating AI tools into the operations of SMEs in Nigeria will enhance their growth and development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were drawn

1. The Government should develop a national strategy for AI that encourages, integrates, and maintains its use among SMEs in Nigeria.
2. It is also suggested that the government and SMEs management should work together to create secure data mechanisms and provide staff training and skill development to enhance AI capabilities.
3. Lastly, the management of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) should work towards creating a smooth integration of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies into their current business operations to achieve optimal growth and development.

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